

Porometric study of polysulphone membranes and their correlation with the performance

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Abstract : The tailor made properties (i.e. pores), are the characteristic of the membrane, through which permeation is controlled. In the membranes, pores can be generated by various methods. Phase inversion technique is the simplest method for the generation of pores. In this study, an attempt is made to establish correlation of water permeability with the porosimetric data for asymmetric membranes of different polymer concentrations, prepared by the phase inversion technique. It was observed that with the increase in polymer concentration, the permeability decreased and the porosimetric data also varied. Changing the filling liquid of different surface tension, a similar trend in porosimetric data was noted. The relative nature of the hydrophobicity in terms of contact angle has been also correlated with the permeation.

Keywords : Porometry, polysulphone, contact angle, water permeability.

One of the important aspects of membrane research is to produce membranes with improved performance in separation science and technology. This is fulfilled by the creation of the pores with in the membrane. There are several methods to introduce and control pore size within the membrane, viz. (i) the incorporation of the metals/ceramics/plastics, (ii) stretching technique, (iii) phase inversion technique and (iv) irradiation technique. Of the various methods, phase inversion technique is the most widely accepted one for the synthesis of asymmetric membrane¹. The structure of membrane with a top skin layer supported by a porous sublayer is the feature of the asymmetric membrane. It brings the heterogeneity of the membrane so that it can be useful in the separation².

The structure along with other feature of the pores are very important to explain the permeation through the asymmetric membrane. In this connection, we have attempted to correlate the permeation with porosity, measured in two liquids of different surface tension. The relative surface nature of the membranes was also studied by contact angle measurement.

Results and discussion

Permeation is the inherent property of the membrane, because pore generation within the membrane not only

the polymer concentration as well as the conditions for casting the membrane. Here, all the other parameters, except polymer concentration were kept constant. The water permeation data (Table 1) showed that the permeation rate depended upon the concentration of the polymer material. The water permeation was inversely proportional to the increase in polymer concentration. As the polymer concentration increased, the pore structures as well as the pore density decreased, it was well reflected in the water flux (PWP) of the membrane.

Polysulfone is hydrophobic in nature. The relative hydrophobicity of different membranes (by varying the polymer concentrations) was measured in terms of contact angle measurement. The contact angle increased with the polymer concentration. It suggested that the water was favorably tried to retain its structure as droplet, rather

Table 1. Variation of water permeability, contact angle with the polymer concentration

Membrane specifications	Polymer concentration (w/w)	Water permeability (GFD)	Normalized contact angle (°)
PS1	15	660	1
PS2	18	160	1.184
PS3	24	12	1.4857

Fig. 1. Pictorial presentation of the contact angles of different membranes (not to scale).

than spreading over the membrane surface. Polysulfone being hydrophobic, the hydrophobicity of the membrane was also increased with the polymer concentration (Fig. 1). Thus, it was observed that the hydrophobicity increased and the permeability decreased with the increase in polymer concentration (Table 1).

From eq. (2), it was also observed that as pore size decreased, (ds/dv) increased and the pressure required to displace the liquid inside the pore was greater. Consequently, the pressure required to empty a pore was determined by magnitude of (ds/dv) at the most constricted part of the pore. The pore, whose constricted pore size was the maximum, required minimum pressure to be emptied and was emptied first. This minimum pressure and the related pore diameter termed as bubble point pressure and bubble point pore diameter respectively. The bubble point pressure and bubble point diameter for the different membranes are compiled in the Table 2. The bubble point pressure increased with the polymer concentration, as it was difficult to blow the liquid in the low pressure. The pore diameter was thus inverse relationship with the polymer concentration. The mean flow pressure and the mean flow pore diameter were also in the same trend as the bubble point pressure and diameter with the polymer concentration. In Table 2 the membrane parameters are enlisted for the wetting liquid

porewick solution as well as water. As $\gamma_{\text{water}} > \gamma_{\text{porewick}}$, the bubble point pressure was low than the value in the specific liquid in case of water.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Polysulfone (Udel, Mw. 35000), dimethyl formamide (Merck) and sodium lauryl sulfate (Merck) were used in the experiment.

The polysulfone membranes of three different concentrations (15, 18 and 24% w/w) were prepared over the non-woven polyester fabric by phase inversion technique using a prototype-casting machine³. The polymer was dissolved in dimethyl formamide, casted on the non-woven fabric and then it was dipped into the non-solvent bath (here water). All the membranes were casted in similar conditions (e.g. humidity, temperature, gelation bath composition and bath temperature). The speed of the motor in casting machine was kept constant in all the cases. Sharp-edge blade with the attachment of the micrometer was used to adjust the thickness of the membranes. Here, for all the membranes the thickness was kept constant. Dimethyl formamide in water and surfactants were used in gelation bath to facilitate the uniform pore generation in the membranes.

The water permeation properties were measured by low-pressure cell. The membranes were pressurized for 1 h, before final reading for permeation. The water permeation data were taken at 2 kg. Here, the effective areas were kept constant for all the membranes. The natures of the membranes were studied by Tensiometer (DCAT 21 from Dataphysics, Germany), by measuring the contact angle in water. Contact angle method is chosen as for

Table 2. Porometric data for different polysulfone membranes

Membrane specifications	Bubble point pressure (psi)	Bubble point pore diameter (μm)	Mean flow pore pressure (psi)	Mean flow pore diameter (μm)
PS1 : in porewick solution	65.62	0.1012	66.475	0.0999
: in water	52.074	0.5738	101.925	0.2932
PS2 : in porewick solution	101.367	0.0655	101.55	0.0654
: in water	60.397	0.4947	131.597	0.2271
PS3 : in porewick solution	122.342	0.0543	122.686	0.0541
: in water	100.76	0.2965	141.339	0.2049

obtaining true surface information of the three-phase (solid/liquid/vapor). This is based on an energy balance approach to the three-phase equilibrium, which results in Young's equation⁴, namely

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\gamma_{sv} - \gamma_{sl}}{\gamma_{lv}} \quad (1)$$

where, γ represents the surface tension for the particular interface.

Considering the pores as a capillary, capillary flow porometer (Porous Materials Inc, USA, Model 1500 AEX) was used to measure the porometric data. In this technique, the membrane samples were soaked in a liquid of low surface tension (viz. Porewick having $\gamma \Rightarrow 16$ dynes/cm² and contact angle being zero) so that it could wet the membrane samples fully and spontaneously filled all the pores in the sample. The other wetting liquid, water, the surface tension was observed at 25 °C ($\gamma \Rightarrow 71$ mN/m). Pressure of the gas on one side of the wet sample was then gradually increased. When the pressure was sufficient to empty the largest pore in the sample, the gas began to flow through the sample. With increasing pressure, the gas removed liquid from smaller pores and the gas flow rate increased. The gas permeation was measured up to 150 psi. The pressure required emptying the pores⁵.

$$p = \gamma_{lg} \cos \theta (ds_{sg} / dv) \quad (2)$$

where dv and ds signifies increase in volume of gas in pore and increase in solid/gas surface area.

The measurement of the porosity and pore properties of the membrane on the capillary flow porometer are based on the physical phenomenon of surface tension of the liquids.

For a pore of circular cross-section of diameter D
 $(ds/dv) = (4/D)$

Hence, with decrease in pore size (ds/dv) increases and the pressure required displacing the liquid inside the pore increases.

The minimum force required to empty the fluid from the pore of the membrane is calculated using the fundamental equation of porometry. The porometry equation could be presented as

$$D = \frac{4 \gamma \cos \theta}{p} \quad (3)$$

D is the diameter of a pore of circular cross-section having the same value of (ds/dv) as that of the pore at its

most constricted part.

When $\theta = 0^\circ$, the equation becomes

$$d = 4\gamma/p \quad (4)$$

here, θ is the contact angle, γ surface tension, p is the differential pressure.

When the pore diameter is plotted against pressure required to expel the fluid from the pore according to this equation curve taken the shape as shown in the Fig. 2, as the pressure approaches to infinity, the pore size approaches to zero.

Fig. 2. Variation of pore diameter with the applied pressure (not to scale).

Reproducibility of the results :

The water permeability data were taken middle portion of the 4 m casted membranes. We had taken three different circles from the middle portion for the water permeation. All the membranes were pressurized for same duration (1 h). The readings were taken three times for the average value. In this case, we used the double distilled water to avoid fouling. The data obtained from different samples of the membranes were taken three times to get the reproducible results. The porometric data were taken two times for the membrane samples side by side, taken from the middle portion.

Conclusion :

Combined porometry and contact angle measurement data is used to characterize asymmetric membranes. The observation is quite clear and according to the theoretical concept. The paper deals with the water permeation data and established the relationship with the contact angle and porosometric parameters. In the porometric study, a better co-relation has been established by permeability

bubble pore diameter and mean pore size, measured by porometry.

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